

Grant Agreement No.: 680708

Project acronym: HIT2GAP

Project title: Highly Innovative building control Tools Tackling the energy performance gap

Research and Innovation Action

Topic: EeB-07-2015 New tools and methodologies to reduce the gap between predicted and actual energy performances at the level of buildings and blocks of buildings

Starting date of project: 1st of September 2015

Duration: 48 months

D7.4 – Dissemination and Awareness Activities Reporting Period 1 – (M01-M18)

Organisation name of lead contractor for this deliverable: NUIG		
Version 2 – Rev.0	Due Date	28 th of February 2017
	Submission Date	28 th of April 2017
	Primary Authors	NUIG – Luis M. Blanes Restoy NUIG – Dr. Bryan McCabe NUIG – Dr. Marcus M. Keane NUIG – Dr. Rory Monaghan
	Contributors	All Partners
	Reviewers	Stephen GARVIN (BRE) Pascale Brassier (NBK)

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

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Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the dissemination and awareness activities conducted by the HIT2GAP project partners according to the marketing strategies planned in Work Package 7 and defined in Deliverable 7.2 – “Marketing Communication Strategy”. The report describes in detail these activities in the next sections as follows, organized in categories:

- Section 2 – Introduces the overall **marketing and dissemination strategy** followed aligned with the scientific objectives of HIT2GAP;
- Section 3 – **Market Diffusion** activities focuses on describing market oriented activities carried out by the project partners. Updated information regarding National Stakeholders Forums is reported in this section. Additionally, EU events and R&D dissemination and awareness activities are also described;
- Section 4 - **Scientific Diffusion** activities deals with (1) Scientific peer reviewed journal publications planned, submitted or published by the HIT2GAP project partners and (2) Conference Communications (Conference Papers, Poster Presentation, Short Communication);
- Section 5 – **Social Media** Communications describes activity metrics and estimated reach of social media instruments such as Flipboard, LinkedIn groups or Twitter, and covers Mass media and other communications;
- Section 6 – **Compendium** summarizes the activities carried out by the consortium members alongside with estimated audience reach, as an abridged account of the HIT2GAP dissemination efforts till date.

During this reporting period (M01 – M18), a significant effort on Dissemination & Awareness activities have been undertaken by the consortium partners, summarizing:

- HIT2GAP partners have conducted a total of 15 Dissemination and Awareness activities;
- In the coming months, there are 2 additional communications actions planned;
- National stakeholder forums are being established in 10 countries – two have held initial meetings;
- Scientific dissemination of HIT2GAP was reflected in 3 submitted Journal papers and 3 participations in peer reviewed conferences. There are two more participations planned in the coming months, one of them in the prestigious Building Simulation Conference “BS 2017 San Francisco” organized by IBPSA (<http://www.buildingsimulation2017.org/>).
- The HIT2GAP Webpage, HIT2GAP Flipboard and Twitter account have been launched;

1 Introduction

HIT2GAP overall objective is to provide a platform that links key enabling technologies, services and approaches used at the operational stage of the building lifecycle in order to narrow the gap between predicted (whereas by design, or by simulation) and actual measured energy performance of buildings. HIT2GAP develops around the provision of an integrative IT platform following a plug-and-play approach. This platform incorporates innovative IT services provided by large system providers and small to medium innovative start-ups services focusing at enhancing and leveraging existing proprietary Building Management Systems functionalities.

1.1 Reporting Periods

This deliverable will be updated during the life of the project according with the project reporting periods as listed in Table 1. For each update period, both planned and carried out activities will be added, updated, or amended comprehensively from the whole project duration till date. The current report corresponds to D7.4 – Reporting Period 1 - Month 1 to Month 18.

Table 1 - D7.4 Reporting Periods

	Reporting Period	Dates Covered	Submission Date
D7.4 – RP0	M1 – M12	Sep 15 – Aug 16	31 st August 2016
D7.4 – RP1	M1 – M18	Sep 15 – Feb 17	28 th February 2017
D7.4 – RP2	M1 – M36	Sep 15 – Aug 18	31 st August 2018
D7.4 – RP3	M1 – M48	Sep 15 – Aug 19	31 st August 2019

1.2 Dissemination and Awareness Strategy

The communication objectives and dissemination strategy of HIT2GAP were described in deliverable D7.2 “Market Communication Strategy”. The aim of this strategy is to overcome typical shortcomings when it comes to real dissemination of research and development projects, industry buy-in and user adoption of energy-related innovative project outcomes. Marketing and communication instruments will ensure that HIT2GAP foreground is adequately explained to the relevant stakeholders reaching the targeted audience.

HIT2GAP will communicate its innovations and novel services using a variety of instruments, from social media to scientific papers. It is intended that at an early stage, the project partners will use the HIT2GAP webpage and newsletter as the main shared communication exchange tool. Public communication materials (Logo, Website, Flyer, Newsletter and Standard Presentation) have been produced and made available to the whole consortium, as reported in deliverable D7.2 - “Public Communication Materials”. During the life of the project, outcomes will be disseminated using specific high impact scientific journal publications and conference participations. As soon as pilot implementations become ready (WP5) and HIT2GAP modules are validated, communication actions will shift towards demonstration events and industry targeted workshops where HIT2GAP foreground can better reach key industry players, government bodies, and other relevant stakeholders.

HIT2GAP Dissemination and Awareness (D&A) strategy will cooperate with other R&D projects under similar topics or H2020 call ensuring coordinated efforts maximize audience reach.

In D7.2 a number of significant aspects concerning the marketing strategy were defined in accordance with the overall HIT2GAP intentions and challenges identified (see D7.2 document for deeper detail), these will be taken into account in this deliverable:

- **HIT2GAP Audiences**, identifies audience type based on impact, influence “on” or “by” the project and potential uptake of project results;
- **HIT2GAP Key Messages**, sets the relevant messages to be delivered to specific audiences;
- **HIT2GAP Communicators**, analyses the role of specific people participating in the project with regards to delivering key messages using different communication channels;
- **HIT2GAP Methods of Communication** enumerates the available communication channels;
- **HIT2GAP Communication Activities and Measurable Outcomes**, classifies the communication activities according with the Objective, Message type, Frequency, Audience and Communicator agent.

In the following sections, the D&A actions performed by the project partners are described. For each action, the relevant performance metrics are disclosed and the relevant HIT2GAP project outcomes or highlights communicated are also mentioned as keywords.

2 Market Diffusion Activities

In this section, Market oriented dissemination and awareness activities are reported. This section encompasses all communications targeted at **Industry groups, Government Agencies, Professional bodies**, and other non-academic-scientific activities. Mass media and social media communication efforts are also excluded from this section.

2.1 National Stakeholders Forums (NSFs)

The following is a summary of D&A activities carried out at a country level by the National Stakeholder Forums (NSF) in the project partners EU member states. The NSFs are composed of representatives of national and local government, professional bodies, agencies, industry and local businesses. The NSFs provide support to the project at a country level and also represents the interest of the country and its key industry sector with regards to HIT2GAP outputs and potential project adoption. The NSF formation process was described in Deliverable D7.2 – Appendix 1: EU Project HIT2GAP: National Stakeholder Forum.

2.1.1 France NSF

Contact point	Pascale BRASSIER (NBK)	pbrassier@nobatek.com
Partners	NBK, BES, LIU, EVL	
Email list size	[No. of companies, institutions, etc. involved] About 30 stakeholders in the field of Facility Management, BMS domain, Energy Management, Building management tools and IHM development	
Meetings held	Initial Meeting – 02/02/2016	The first meeting was conducted in the frame of the Innovation Workshop organised by PROMODUL with French actors such as Trend, Schneider Electric, VELUX, VINCI Construction, Saint Gobain.
	Meeting 1 – A second meeting was held 22 nd March 2017 with a larger targeted audience	[Highlights]
	Meeting 2 – [Date]	[Highlights]
	Meeting 3 – [Date]	[Highlights]
Planned Activities	Activity 1 - Workshop targeting different stakeholder categories (Facility Managers, BMS providers, Energy Managers, Buildings and estates managers, start-ups in the field of building measurement, IHM, software for energy management) Planned March 2017	
	Activity 2 - [Description]	

	Activity 3 - [Description]
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2.1.2 Ireland NSF

Contact point	Luis M. Blanes Restoy	hit2gap-ireland@googlegroups.com
Partners	NUIG – ZUT – CYL – ENE	
Email list size	50 mail list subscribers	
Meetings held	Initial Meeting held 13 March 2017	Proposed 2 events to disseminate HIT2GAP Created HIT2GAP googlegroups Ireland
	Meeting 1 planned 1 st . Week June 2017	[Highlights]
	Meeting 2	[Highlights]
	Meeting 3	[Highlights]
Planned Activities	Activity 1 – CPD workshop at NUIG targeting ASHRAE Ireland, Engineers Ireland (EI) and CIBSE Ireland members. Planned May 2016.	
	Activity 2 – Proposed presentation at one of the CiTA BIM events. (date TBC) CiTA (http://www.cita.ie) is the main stakeholders body in charge of promoting boosting digital construction agenda in Ireland.	
	Activity 3 - [Description]	

2.1.3 Spain NSF

Contact point	Gorka Naveran	gorka.naveran@veolia.com
Partners	GIR-TEK-EUR-UDG	
Email list size	16 mail list subscribers	
Meetings held	Initial Meeting	TBC
	Meeting 1 – [Date]	[Highlights]
	Meeting 2 – [Date]	[Highlights]
	Meeting 3 – [Date]	[Highlights]
Planned Activities	Smartcity Expo World Congress & European Utility Week (November 2016): Meeting in the fair premises or nearby, taking advantage of the presence of relevant stakeholders; Information and leaflets available in the booth	
	City of San Sebastian and Vitoria (Last quarter 2016): Meeting with local authorities to present HIT2GAP project, gather feedback and ask support for dissemination	
	EVE, The Basque Government's energy agency (Last quarter 2016): Meeting with energy agency staff to present HIT2GAP project and gather feedback	

2.1.4 Poland NSF

Contact point	Piotr Dymarski	p.dymarski@mostostal.waw.pl
Partners	MOS, WRS	
Email list size	TBC	
Meetings held	Initial Meeting – 24 May 2017	A meeting is planned with the Managing Director in Poland of International Business Contracts to discuss HIT2GAP modules and potential platform capabilities against other solutions.
	Meeting 1 – [Date]	[Highlights]
	Meeting 2 – [Date]	[Highlights]
	Meeting 3 – [Date]	[Highlights]
Planned Activities	Activity 1 - [Description]	
	Activity 2 - [Description]	
	Activity 3 - [Description]	

2.1.5 UK NSF

Contact point	Stephen Garvin	GarvinS@bre.co.uk
Partners	BRE, UoS	
Email list size	12 (excluding the project team)	
Meetings held	Initial Meeting – 16 Aug 2016	A stakeholder meeting was held at the BRE Innovation Park in Ravenscraig on 16 August 2016. Presentations were given by BRE and UOS, followed by discussions where attendees were asked to consider a number of questions relevant to HIT2GAP. Post-occupancy evaluation, second tier trial buildings and adventitious electrical loads due to building occupiers were all discussed.
	Meeting 1 – 26 April 2017	A stakeholder meeting is planned to take place in April 2017 in East Kilbride. The meeting will include discussions of some of the HIT2GAP modules that are being developed.
	Meeting 2 – [Date]	[Highlights]
	Meeting 3 – [Date]	[Highlights]
Planned Activities	Activity 1 - [Description]	
	Activity 2 - [Description]	
	Activity 3 - [Description]	

2.1.6 Cyprus NSF

Contact point	Dr. Stavros Hadjiyiannis	stavros@cyric.eu
Partners	CYR	
Email list size	25 email subscribers	
Meetings held	Initial Meeting	TBC
	Meeting 1 – [Date]	[Highlights]
	Meeting 2 – [Date]	[Highlights]
	Meeting 3 – [Date]	[Highlights]
Planned Activities	October 2015 – Diffusion of newsletter on latest activities of HIT2GAP	
	Activity 2 - [Description]	
	Activity 3 - [Description]	

2.1.7 Germany NSF

Contact point	Nicolas Réhault	Nicolas.Rehault@ise.fraunhofer.de
Partners	FISE	
Email list size	TBC	
Meetings held	Initial Meeting – 3 May 2017	Fraunhofer ISE will run the German NSF. Their first meeting is planned for 3 May 2017 in Berlin at the forthcoming Berliner Energietage.
	Meeting 1 – [Date]	[Highlights]
	Meeting 2 – [Date]	[Highlights]
	Meeting 3 – [Date]	[Highlights]
Planned Activities	Activity 1 - Workshop at M22/23 (June/July 2017) in Freiburg	
	Activity 2 - Workshop at M45/46 (location in Germany to be defined)	
	Activity 3 - [Description]	

2.1.8 Italy NSF

Contact point	Gianluca Signore	gianluca.signore@r2msolution.com
Partners	R2M – ABO	
Email list size	About 50	
Meetings held	Initial Meeting - January 2017	The meeting present HIT2GAP to stakeholders and illustrate them on how to benefit from HIT2GAP outputs.
	Meeting 1 – [Date]	[Highlights]
	Meeting 2 – [Date]	[Highlights]
	Meeting 3 – [Date]	[Highlights]

Planned Activities	Targeted discussion with Facility management organisations and Local Engineering chapter
	Activity 2 - [Description]
	Activity 3 - [Description]

2.1.9 Greece NSF

Contact point	TBC	[email]
Partners	API	
Email list size	TBC	
Meetings held	November 2016	APINTECH presented HIT2GAP in the Hotelia exhibition, Thessaloniki, Greece, in November 2016, where they disseminated to about 30 potential clients in the hotel and resort housing sectors.
	Meeting 1 – [Date]	[Highlights]
	Meeting 2 – [Date]	[Highlights]
	Meeting 3 – [Date]	[Highlights]
Planned Activities	Activity 1 - [Description]	
	Activity 2 - [Description]	
	Activity 3 - [Description]	

2.1.10 Turkey NSF

Contact point	Gulben Calis	gulbencalis@gmail.com
Partners	EGE	
Email list size	38	
Meetings held	Initial Meeting – Sep 2016	EGE University premises
	Meeting 1 – [Date]	[Highlights]
	Meeting 2 – [Date]	[Highlights]
	Meeting 3 – [Date]	[Highlights]
Planned Activities	Activity 1 - Introduction of HIT2GAP project and initial feedback from stakeholders (planned in October 2016)	
	Activity 2 - [Description]	
	Activity 3 - [Description]	

2.2 Market Dissemination and Awareness Activities

2.2.1 Dissemination and Awareness activities performed during RP1 [M01-M18]

Name	Workshop SmartTABCD			01
Action type	WS-AC, WS-I			
Location	Biarritz-Anglet-Bayonne, France.	Date	14/09/2015	
Partners	NBK, FISE, API, R2M, NUIG, UOS, TEC, ENE, UDG			
Link	http://aiai2015.sigappfr.org/			
Description	SmarTABCD'15 Workshop Smart Technologies and Applications on Buildings, Cities and Districts Bayonne Château-Neuf – France International Conference on Artificial Intelligence Application and Innovations (AIAI'15)			
Audience type	I-SW, HEI	Reach	100	
Key Messages	<p>Disseminate the HIT2GAP approach to the researches and industrials that are participating to this workshop</p> <p>The HIT2GAP partners presented the tools they bring into the HIT2GAP project.</p> <p>Present and Discuss:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Routing Protocol for Wireless Multimedia Sensor Networks - Model Occupant Satisfaction and Behavior in a Building - Energy Management Decision Making - City Scale Modeling <p>Data Driven Platform for Energy Efficiency Monitoring</p>			
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and Deliverables			

Name	Sustainable Places 2015			02
Action type	CONF			
Location	Savona, Italy	Date	18/09/2015	
Partners	R2M			
Link	http://sustainable-places.eu/past-events/sp-2015/			
Description	Sustainable Places 2015 builds on the two previous successful events in 2013 and 2014. This third edition was an original initiative from the RESILIENT and PERFORMER FP7 European project consortiums, aiming to generate a successful, sustainable and world-class series of annual conferences. Sustainable Places 2015 aimed to gather scientists, researchers, and engineers, from research institutes and the			

	industry, around one of the greatest challenges that our societies have ever faced: ensuring long-term environmental sustainability of ever-growing, densifying urban areas, in a resource-constrained world.		
Audience type	I-SW, HEI	Reach	50
Key Messages	Overall description of projects, innovations and ambitions		
	[Key Message 2]		
	[Key Message 3]		
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and Deliverables		

Name	3 rd Innovation Workshop organised by PROMODUL	03
Action type	WS-I, INEF4	
Location	Paris, France	Date 02/02/2016
Partners	NBK	
Link	http://www.cercle-promodul.fr/3eme-edition-ateliers-innovation-inef4	
Description	As a founder member of INEF4 (Factor 4 National Innovation & Excellence Institute), the Cercle Promodul Association has implemented some working groups entitled "Innovation Workshops". These workshops are reserved for industrial members of the Cercle Promodul and enable discussions with projects managers leading INEF4 and H2020 projects and therefore benefit from the last R&D developments.	
Audience type	I-BMS, PB-CM, PB-BS	Reach 10
Key Messages	Disseminate the HIT2GAP approach and discuss with industrials and specifically with BMS providers.	
	[Key Message 2]	
	[Key Message 3]	
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and Deliverables	

Name	Expert Seminar on energy performance measurement of buildings	04
Action type	SEM	
Location	Louveciennes, France	Date 10/02/2016
Partners	NBK	
Link	http://www.adecom13.fr/NL0715/AMI_MPEB.pdf	
Description	Presentation of HIT2GAP at expert seminar dedicated to Buildings Energy Performance Management. Organised by the FEB (Fondation Batiment Energie).	
Audience type	PB, G-N, I-BMS, I-SW, I-ESCO, PB-EN, PB-CM, PB-BS, P-FM, EU-H2020, RI	Reach 40
Key Messages	Disseminate HIT2GAP Approach	
	[Key Message 2]	
	[Key Message 3]	
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and Deliverables	

Name	Ecobuild			05
Action type	EXH, CONF			
Location	London, UK	Date	8/03/2016	
Partners	BRE			
Link	http://ecobuild.co.uk			
Description	Exhibition and conference used to raise awareness of HIT2GAP project within the construction industry at this 3-days event, which focusses on innovations in construction. BRE used its exhibition stand and speaker slots to do this.			
Audience type	All	Reach	800	
Key Messages	[Key Message 1]			
	[Key Message 2]			
	[Key Message 3]			
HIT2GAP connection	[WPs, Tasks, Deliverables] [Exploitable Results Presented]			

Name	EeB Impact Workshop			06
Action type	EU-EEB			
Location	Brussels, BE	Date	19/04/2016	
Partners	R2M			
Link	http://ec.europa.eu/research/index.cfm?pg=events&eventcode=726793D4-9B63-B6E2-A5C2649F019492E3			
Description	The EeB Impact Workshop is organised by the European Commission with the EeB PPP project representatives. The focus this year is again on generating impact, exploiting synergies and clustering the potential of projects which belong to the same area of research and innovation.			
Audience type	EU-H2020	Reach	50	
Key Messages	[Key Message 1]			
	[Key Message 2]			
	[Key Message 3]			
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and Deliverables			

Name	4th Industrial Technologies Conference			07
Action type	CONF			
Location	Amsterdam, Netherlands	Date	22/06/2016	
Partners	R2M			
Link	http://www.industrialtechnologies2016.eu/			
Description	European Conference held in the RAI in Amsterdam promoting the field of new production technologies, materials, nanotechnology and digitisation. It is the largest of its kind in Europe with more than 12,500 delegates, held over three days.			

Audience type	[From ANNEX 2 – Audience Type]	Reach	500
Key Messages	Overall presentation of projects, innovations and potential benefits for users.		
	[Key Message 2]		
	[Key Message 3]		
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and Deliverables		

Name	Sustainable Places 2016	08
Action type	CONF	
Location	Anglet, France	Date 29/06/2016
Partners	NBK, R2M, NUIG	
Link	http://sustainable-places.eu/sp-2016/	
Description	<p>Sustainable Places 2016 aims to gather scientists, researchers, and engineers, from research institutes and the industry, around one of the greatest challenges that our societies have ever faced: ensuring the long-term environmental sustainability of ever-growing, densifying urban areas, in a resource-constrained world. A workshop has been organized during the conference gathering the sister projects of HIT2GAP:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - TOPAs (coord. MOTOROLA Solutions), - QUANTUM (coord. IGS), and - MOEEBIUS (coord. TECNALIA). 	
Audience type	EU-H2020, PP	Reach 15
Key Messages	Overall description of projects and solutions	
	Identification of possible exploitation route for the project alone or jointly among sister projects	
	<p>HIT2GAP, TOPAs, QUANTUM & MOEEBIUS projects: New tools to reduce the energy performances gap.</p> <p>Four European H2020 funded projects, HIT2GAP, TOPAs, QUANTUM and MOEEBIUS, will work to provide new tools and methodologies to minimise the gap between the predicted and the actual energy usage in buildings and blocks of buildings. The workshop aims at initiating clustering around this topic and discussing the solutions developed as part of the projects.</p>	
HIT2GAP connection	<p>Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and Deliverables</p> <p>WP6 due to exploitation synergies</p> <p>Whole project and clustering strategy</p>	

Name	EESAP 2016	09
Action type	CONF	
Location	San Sebastian, Spain	Date 04/07/2016
Partners	NBK	
Link	http://eesap.eu/language/es/inicio/	
Description	EESAP is a European conference on energy efficiency and sustainability in architecture and planning/urbanism. A poster related to the HIT2GAP approach and the envisioned platform has been presented during the conference.	
Audience type	PP, G-N, G-EN, HEI, PB-AR, PB-CM	Reach 25
Key Messages	Disseminate the HIT2GAP approach to the research and education groups of the Basque Government, as well as other national and international institutions related to the fields of the climate change, energy efficiency and environmental sustainability	
	Present building energy efficiency solution applied in the project	
	[Key Message 3]	
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and Deliverables; Presentation of the whole project focusing on the functional platform architecture.	

Name	Cities of the Future	10
Action type	H2020	
Location	Istanbul, Turkey	Date 30/09/2016
Partners	EGE	
Link	https://www.b2match.eu/futurecities-h2020	
Description	Poster presentation of HIT2GAP at the "Cities of the Future Brokerage Event" in Istanbul which is co-financed by European Union and TÜBİTAK.	
Audience type	[From ANNEX 2 – Audience Type]	Reach 300
Key Messages	[Key Message 1]	
	[Key Message 2]	
	[Key Message 3]	
HIT2GAP connection	[WPs, Tasks, Deliverables] [Exploitable Results Presented]	

Name	MEDES '16 (8 th International Conference on Management of Digital EcoSystems)	11
Action type	CONF	
Location	Hendaye, France	Date 02-03-04/11/2016
Partners	NBK, LIU	
Link	http://medes.sigappfr.org/16/	
Description	The International Conference on Management of Digital EcoSystems	

	<p>(MEDES), previously named "The International Conference on Management of Emergent Digital EcoSystems", aims to develop and bring together a diverse community from academia, research laboratories and industry interested in exploring the manifold challenges and issues related to web technologies and resource management of Digital Ecosystems and how current approaches and technologies can be evolved and adapted to this end.</p> <p>The HIT2GAP project has been presented during the special session on Smart Grids and Smart buildings.</p> <p>Presentation Title: "<i>Hit2Gap - Towards a Collaborative Smart Building Management System Solution</i>".</p>		
Audience type	PP, HEI, PB-EN, PB-IT, PB-BS	Reach	40
Key Messages	Disseminate the HIT2GAP approach to the research and education groups of the Basque Government, as well as other national and international institutions related to the fields of the climate change, energy efficiency and environmental sustainability		
	Present the HIT2GAP solution applied in the project		
	[Key Message 3]		
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and Deliverables; Presentation of the whole project focusing on the functional platform architecture.		

Name	ISA BTP Business Forum		12
Action type	EDU		
Location	Anglet, France	Date	10/11/2016
Partners	NBK		
Link			
Description	NOBATEK presented the on-going work conducted within the HIT2GAP project at Higher Institute of building and Civil Engineering of Aquitaine. This event marked the 20 th year celebration event of the ISA BTP business forum.		
Audience type	HEI	Reach	30
Key Messages	Disseminate the HIT2GAP approach.		
	[Key Message 2]		
	[Key Message 3]		
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and Deliverables; Flyer distribution.		

Name	EINSTEIN – HIT2GAP Workshop		13
Action type	WS-AC		
Location	Galway, Ireland	Date	14/11/2016
Partners	NUIG, ZUT, CYL		
Link	http://www.einstein-iapp.eu/news https://www.iesve.com/discoveries/blog/2nd-einstein-workshop-ies-building-operations-research-update/		
Description	The second EINSTEIN project workshop was hosted at the Engineering		

	<p>Building at the National University of Ireland Galway last Monday 14th November. The workshop, kindly hosted by the College of Engineering and Informatics (CoEI), provided an opportunity for our building operations team to engage with building stakeholders, students, researchers and external companies, in order to showcase current work and identify opportunities for collaboration.</p> <p>The workshop opened with a tour of the state-of-the-art engineering building at NUI Galway, led by Mr. Aodh Dalton (Chief Technical Officer, College of Engineering and Informatics). Attendees from NUIG-IRUSE, Trinity College Dublin (TCD), IES, Cylon Controls, and ZuTec, were given a guided tour of the building labs, lecture theatres and dedicated energy centre.</p>		
Audience type	PP, RI, HEI	Reach	20
Key Messages	Showcase of HIT2GAP and opportunity for cross collaboration at academic, and industry-academia levels.		
	Stakeholders feedback and information collaboration resulted in a fruitful engagement with NUIG Buildings Office and Facility Managers with views of implementing optimised smart solutions coming from HIT2GAP.		
	Presentation of " The Battle of Buildings ", a NUIG Strategy sustainability awareness and participative project and opportunities to showcase and exploit HIT2GAP outputs through the whole academic community.		
HIT2GAP connection	WP5 – Demonstration in NEB Irish Pilot; WP7 – Stakeholders feedback; Task 1.6 Display Modules, Task 2.4 and Task 3.4 on Building Simulation		

Name	7 th ECTP conference 2016-Innovative Built Environment		14
Action type	CONF, EU-EEB		
Location	Brussels, Belgium	Date	17-18/11/2016
Partners	NBK		
Link	https://fr.xing-events.com/ECTPConference2016.html		
Description	<p>The 7th ECTP conference is organized by the European Construction Technology Platform (ECTP). This event is dedicated to present and discuss current and anticipated innovation in the built environment field (including the issue of energy efficiency of buildings).</p> <p>During the conference, a hall was dedicated to booths and posters that exhibited examples of innovation expected from European projects. This exhibition gave us the opportunity to present the HIT2GAP solution together with two other innovative products coming from H2020 projects: BUILT2SPEC and E2VENT.</p>		
Audience type	PP, PB, G-EN, RFA, FI, HEI, EU-H2020	Reach	200
Key Messages	Disseminate the HIT2GAP approach, find synergies and share experience with other projects.		
	Present the HIT2GAP innovative solution developed in the project		
	[Key Message 3]		
HIT2GAP	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and Deliverables; Presentation of the		

connection	whole project: context, objectives and developed solutions.		
Name	Article in Energy Efficiency dissemination portal EnergiImpulse	15	
Action type	CONF, EU-EEB		
Location	Brussels, Belgium	Date	17-18/11/2016
Partners	FISE		
Link	http://www.berliner-impulse.de/fileadmin/user_upload/berliner-impulse/01_Aktuell/03_Zeitschrift/2017/1_2017/Energie-ImpulsE_01_2017_gesamt_WEB.pdf		
Description	Article in Berliner Energie Impulse e-magazine		
Audience type	CON, P-FM,	Reach	500
Key Messages	Disseminate the HIT2GAP approach to general public in a specialized energy efficiency magazine in Germany		
	Present the HIT2GAP innovative solution developed in the project		
	[Key Message 3]		
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and Deliverables; Presentation of the whole project: context, objectives and developed solutions.		

2.2.2 Dissemination and awareness activities planned in RP2 [M01-M36]

Name	Building Simulation 2017	16
Action type	CONF	
Location	San Francisco, USA	Date 07/08/2017
Partners	BRE, UOS	
Link	http://www.buildingsimulation2017.org/ www.ibpsa.org	
Description	Building Simulation 2017 will bring together practitioners and researchers from around the world to share information about the state of the art in simulation tools and applications and to discuss new developments. The conference will feature updates and insights regarding new research to improve simulation capabilities for advanced low-energy building systems, case studies from successful projects that demonstrate the key role that simulation plays, and ongoing efforts to enable compliance and building rating software to support radiant and other energy efficient systems.	
Audience type	[From <u>ANNEX 2 – Audience Type</u>]	Reach 800
Key Messages	To promote HIT2GAP at the largest Building Simulation research and practice event in the world.	
	[Key Message 2]	
	[Key Message 3]	
HIT2GAP connection	[WPs, Tasks, Deliverables] [Exploitable Results Presented]	

Name	CISBAT 2017 [Abstract sent]			17
Action type	CONF			
Location	Lausanne, Switzerland	Date	06-08/09/2017	
Partners	NBK			
Link	http://cisbat.epfl.ch/index.html			
Description	<p>Focused on energy efficiency and the use of solar energy in the built environment, CISBAT offers a dynamic international platform for scientific exchange in fields ranging from nanostructured materials for renewable energy applications to urban energy systems.</p> <p>CISBAT is organised for the 14th time by the Solar Energy and Building Physics Lab (LESO-PB) of the Swiss Federal Institute of Technology Lausanne (EPFL).</p> <p>Academic partners of the conference are renowned scientists from the University of Cambridge and the MIT as well as the Swiss Competence Center for Energy Research "Future Energy Efficient Buildings & Districts" and the Swiss chapter of the International Building Performance Simulation Association IBPSA, backed by a strong international scientific committee.</p>			
Audience type	[From ANNEX 2 – Audience Type]	Reach	300	
Key Messages	Paper focused on the HIT2GAP architecture			
	[Key Message 2]			
	[Key Message 3]			
HIT2GAP connection	[WPs, Tasks, Deliverables] [Exploitable Results Presented]			

3 Scientific Diffusion Activities

Scientific diffusion activities target academic and scientific audiences. As H2020 project, HIT2GAP partners have the obligation to make sure peer-reviewed journal articles published are openly accessible and free of charge.

3.1 Scientific Publication Strategy

HIT2GAP scientific publication strategy and guidelines has been outlined in Deliverable 7.2-Appendix 3: “Guidelines for preparation of conference/journal papers.

3.2 Peer Reviewed Journal Papers published

Title	“Short-term load forecasting for non-residential buildings contrasting artificial occupancy attributes”
Authors	J. Massana, C. Pous, L. Burgas, J. Meléndez, J. Colomer
HIT2GAP partners	UDG
Journal Name	Energy and Buildings
Journal Impact	2.973 (2015)
Correspondence	joaquim.melendez@udg.edu
DOI	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2016.08.081
HIT2GAP relevance	WP1, Task 1.3
Abstract	<p>An accurate short-term load forecasting system allows an optimum daily operation of the power system and a suitable process of decision-making, such as with regard to control measures, resource planning or initial investment, to be achieved. In a previous work, the authors demonstrated that an SVR model to forecast the electric load in a non-residential building using only the temperature and occupancy of the building as attributes is the one that gives the best balance of accuracy and computational cost for the cases under study. Starting from this conclusion, a simple, low-computational requirements and economical hourly consumption prediction method, based on SVR model and only the calculated occupancy indicator as attribute, is proposed. The method, unlike the others, is able to perform hourly predictions months in advance using only the occupancy indicator.</p> <p>Due to the relevance of the occupancy indicator in the model, this paper provides a complete study of the methods and data sources employed in the creation of the artificial occupancy attributes. Several occupancy indicators are defined, from the simplest one, using general information, to the most complex one, based on very detailed information. Then, a load forecasting performance discrimination between the artificial occupancy attributes is realized demonstrating that using the most complex indicator increases the workload and complexity while not improving the load prediction significantly. A real case study, applying</p>

	the forecasting method to several non-residential buildings in the University of Girona, serve as a demonstration.
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Title	Identifying services for short-term load forecasting using data driven models in a Smart City platform
Authors	Burgas Nadal, Llorenç; Meléndez i Frigola, Joaquim; Colomer Llinàs, Joan; Pous i Sabadí, Carles; Massana i Raurich, Joaquim
HIT2GAP partners	UDG
Journal Name	Sustainable Cities and Society
Journal Impact	1.044 (2015)
Correspondence	joaquim.massana@udg.edu
DOI	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2016.09.001
HIT2GAP relevance	WP1, Task 1.3
Abstract	The paper describes an ongoing work to embed several services in a Smart City architecture with the aim of achieving a sustainable city. In particular, the main goal is to identify services required in such framework to define the requirements and features of a reference architecture to support the data-driven methods for energy efficiency monitoring or load prediction. With this object in mind, a use case of short-term load forecasting in non-residential buildings in the University of Girona is provided, in order to practically explain the services embedded in the described general layers architecture. In the work, classic data-driven models for load forecasting in buildings are used as an example.

Title	Compatibility of municipal services based on service similarity
Authors	R. Rusek, M.L. Marsal, F. Torrent, J. Colomer
HIT2GAP partners	UDG
Journal Name	Cities
Journal Impact	2.051 (2015)
Correspondence	joan.colomer@udg.edu
DOI	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2016.05.024
HIT2GAP relevance	WP2, Task 2.5
Abstract	The aim of this article is to propose and examine a quantitative method of determining the degree of compatibility between municipal services. Provision of services and facilities maintenance are usually two biggest expenditures of local governments. Traditionally, facilities host only one service, whereas the challenge and opportunity lies in combining various, compatible services and offering them together under one roof. Such a combination decreases municipal expenditure and has a strong positive impact on the general service quality. For this purpose, we take advantage of the City-block distance formula to calculate the degree of compatibility between municipal services. The method is examined and discussed on a sample of 30 real municipal services. This allows us to find possible combinations of strongly compatible services that should be offered together in Multi-Service Facilities and, at the same time, avoid an unwanted combination of services that are incompatible.

3.3 Scientific Conference Papers

Title	Towards a Data Driven Platform for Energy Efficiency Monitoring: Two Use Cases
Authors	<i>Melendez, Joaquim; Colomer, Joan; Pous, Carles; Burgas, Llorenç; Massana, Joaquim</i>
HIT2GAP partners	UDG
Conference	11th International Conference on Artificial Intelligence Applications and Innovations (AIAI 2015): Vol-1539
Correspondence	joaquim.melendez@udg.edu
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.400290
HIT2GAP relevance	WP1, Task 1.3
Abstract	The paper describes an ongoing work to define a framework to support monitoring procedures for distribution systems in smart cities. Specific use cases, involving data driven methods for energy monitoring, benchmarking and forecasting in urban scenarios are analysed. The objective is to identify services required in such framework to define the requirements of a reference architecture to support data-driven methods for energy efficiency monitoring and assessment. Use cases focus on multi-entity buildings monitoring and consumption forecasting.

Title	Recent Developments in City Scale Modelling, Monitoring and Performance Information Delivery
Authors	<i>Joe Clarke</i>
HIT2GAP partners	UOS
Conference	11th International Conference on Artificial Intelligence Applications and Innovations (AIAI 2015): Vol-1539
Correspondence	joe@esru.strath.ac.uk
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.400289
HIT2GAP relevance	WP1, Task 1.3, Task 1.4
Abstract	This paper corresponds to a presentation delivered at the SmarTABCD' 15 workshop on Smart Technologies and Applications in Buildings, Cities and Districts organised within the framework of the 11th International Conference on Artificial Intelligence Applications and Innovations. It reports outcomes from recent research that established a means to deliver, rapidly and at low cost, energy-related apps corresponding to discrete issues such as inappropriate HVAC system regulation, occupant discomfort avoidance, energy use reporting, upgrade quality assurance and the like.

Title	A Methodology to Develop a User-Behaviour Tool to Optimize Building Users' Comfort and Energy Use
Authors	<i>Gulben Calis¹, Aitor Corchero Rodriguez², Türkan Göksal-Özbalta¹, Regina Enrich Sard², Aitor Arnaiz³, Ignacio Lazaro³, Nikos Sakkas⁴</i>
HIT2GAP partners	EGE, EUR, TEK, API
Conference	SBE 16 Istanbul
Correspondence	Gulben.calis@ege.edu.tr
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.398828
HIT2GAP relevance	To promote HIT2GAP aligned with Task 7.3

Abstract	<p>The total amount of energy spent in buildings is quite significant, reaching up to 40% of the world's total energy usage. Accordingly, the EU has set goals requiring zero CO₂ emission in buildings by 2020 to respond to the increasing energy demand and started continuously supporting innovative research approaches for improving energy efficiency in buildings. However, innovative approaches cover the challenges in specific parts (specific facilities, building functionalities, etc.) of both new buildings and renovation of existing buildings. Therefore, main challenge in current building facilities is scaling up of the building innovative approaches in combination with the building usage. So, it is crucial to influence the complex interaction between users and buildings. To reinforce the building configuration and adaption according to the occupants' behaviour, this paper presents a methodology to construct a building-user interaction. This methodology aims at developing data mining algorithms and semantic models with stream reasoning capabilities that allows occupants and facility managers to monitor and control the energy consumption, to detect the energy inefficiencies and to generate recommendations to reduce energy consumption whilst increasing occupant comfort. The proposed methodology is modular which could be integrated in the existing building management systems and that is promising to reduce energy use in existing buildings.</p>
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3.4 Scientific Conferences in Preparation/Review

Title	Methodology for Evaluating the Performance Gap
Authors	<i>Gesa Angelika Benndorf, Luis Carlos Chamorro Romero, Nicolas Réhault</i>
HIT2GAP partners	FISE
Conference	Building Simulation 2017
Correspondence	gesa.benndorf@ise.fraunhofer.de
DOI	N/A
HIT2GAP relevance	To promote HIT2GAP aligned with Task 2.4/3.4
Abstract	<p>The discrepancy between design intents and actual energy performance during the operation of buildings, the so-called performance gap, has been widely discussed in the literature. Here, we focus on the gap between simulated and measured energy consumption. From the recent literature it becomes evident that there is a need for methods which aim at reducing the performance gap. However, to the author's knowledge there exists no approach which systematically analyzes the performance gap for a given building, evaluates the reasons for it and, based on this reasoning, provides recommendations for remedying the gap. Here, we propose a methodology for comparing the results of a building simulation to measurement data. In case of a significant discrepancy in the energy consumption, possible reasons for the discrepancy are step by step analysed until at the end of the routine one or several reasons are identified as the ones causing the gap. Based on this evaluation, recommendations for reducing the gap can be deduced.</p>

3.5 Peer Reviewed Papers – Summary

Authors	Year	Title	Journal
(Massana et.al)		Short-term load forecasting for non-residential buildings contrasting artificial occupancy attributes	Energy and Buildings
(Massana et.al)		Identifying services for short-term load forecasting using data driven models in a Smart City platform	Sustainable Cities and Society
(Rusek et.al)		Compatibility of municipal services based on service similarity	Cities

3.6 Peer Reviewed Conference Participations - Summary

Date	Participation	Partner	Conference Name	Location	Est. Audience Size
14-17/09/2015	Full paper presentation	UOS	AIAI 2015	Bayonne, France	50
14-17/09/2015	Full paper presentation	UDG	AIAI 2015	Bayonne, France	50
13-15/10/2016	Full paper presentation	EGE, EUR, TEK, API	SBE 16 Istanbul	Istanbul, Turkey	50
In Preparation or Review					
07-09/09/2017	Full paper presentation	FISE	BS 2017 San Francisco	S. Francisco, CA- US	800

4 Social Media Communications

4.1 HIT2GAP Web Page Communication activity report

HIT2GAP webpage was launched in September 2015. The site has received **4904 page views** from the start date in September 2015 until 28 February 2017. HIT2GAP Website is accessible from www.hit2gap.eu. The initial webpage is undertaking a redesign process to include the following features:

- Live tweeter feeds of the HIT2GAP account;
- Document section with downloadable links to public deliverables and dissemination papers;
- A new web layout with pictures and media support;
- National Stakeholders Forums section with contact points.

Figure 1 – The HIT2GAP new webpage layout (www.hit2gap.eu)

Figure 2 below, provided by Google, shows a summary statistical view of the HIT2GAP webpage from Sep 2015 till February 2017.

© 2017 Google

Figure 2 - Summary Statistics for www.hit2gap.eu website

4.2 HIT2GAP Newsletter and additional communications

HIT2GAP first newsletter was issued last February 2016.

Below statistics of the first Newsletter are shown. The newsletter is available here: <http://en.calameo.com/read/0046186047b57624d9b9f>

HIT2GAP second newsletter was issued last November 2016.

Below statistics of the first Newsletter are shown. The newsletter is available here: <http://eepurl.com/cnBEwP>

4.2.1 HIT2GAP - Newsletter One – Statistics

Newsletter One Statistics are based on three different mailing lists which were used to disseminate the Newsletter, user *MailChimp.com*. Below we show the summary statistics for these three mail lists. Currently there are no statistics tracking available showing direct downloads of the Newsletter from the HIT2GAP webpage.

HIT2GAP Project Team Mailing List – sent to 264 recipients via MailChimp	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subject: HIT2GAP - First Project Newsletter is Published! • Delivered: Tue, Mar 29, 2016 1:25 pm 	
Open and Clicks	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open rate 39.7% • List average 36.7% • Industry average (Construction) 19.1% 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Click rate 13.5% • List average 13.1% • Industry average (Construction) 1.8%
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No. of people who opened – 100 • No. of people who clicked – 34 • Bounced – 12 • Unsubscribed – 4 • Successful deliveries – 252 (95.5%) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total opens – 287 (includes multiple by same person) • Forwarded – 0 • Clicks per unique opens – 34.0% • Total clicks – 52
Top links clicked	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 23 – download pdf • 21 – http://www.hit2gap.eu/blog/first-hit2gap-project-newsletter • 8 – project website 	

C4R – sent to 361 recipients via MailChimp

- Subject: HIT2GAP - First Project Newsletter is Published!
- Delivered: 3/29/16 2:48PM

Open and Clicks

- | | |
|--|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open rate <u>32.8%</u> • List average 31.3% • Industry average (Construction) 19.1% | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Click rate 6.7% • List average 5.9% • Industry average (Construction) 1.8% |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No. of people who opened – 117 • No. of people who clicked – 24 • Bounced – 4 • Unsubscribed – 2 • Successful deliveries – 357 (98.9%) | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total opens – 241 (includes multiple by same person) • Forwarded – 0 • Clicks per unique opens – <u>20.5%</u> • Total clicks – 32 |

Top links clicked

- 18 – download pdf
- 12 – <http://www.hit2gap.eu/blog/first-hit2gap-project-newsletter>
- 2 – project website

Location: 100% UK

Enerit – sent to 499 recipients via MailChimp

- Subject: Closing the Gap in Building Energy Performance - HIT2GAP an EU H2020 Project
- Delivered: Apr 01, 2016 04:00 pm

Open and Clicks

- | | |
|--|---|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open rate <u>25.1%</u> • List average 22.1% • Industry average (Software and Web App) 17.7% | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Click rate <u>6.0%</u> • List average 3.5% • Industry average (Software and Web App) 2.0% |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No. of people who opened – 104 • No. of people who clicked – 25 • Bounced – 84 • Unsubscribed – 3 | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total opens – 277 (includes multiple by same person) • Forwarded – 0 • Clicks per unique opens – <u>24.0%</u> |

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Successful deliveries – 415 (83.2%) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total clicks – <u>46</u> 																				
Top links clicked																					
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 6 – http://www.hit2gap.eu/blog/first-hit2gap-project-newsletter • 20 – download pdf 																					
<p><i>Top locations by opens</i></p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>	France	1	7.7%																		
	Ireland	3	23.1%																		
	Italy	3	23.1%																		
	United Kingdom	2	15.4%																		
	USA	2	15.4%																		
	France	1	7.7%																		

4.2.2 HIT2GAP - Newsletter Two – Statistics

Newsletter One Statistics are based on three different mailing lists which were used to disseminate the Newsletter, user *MailChimp.com*. Below we show the summary statistics for the six email lists considered. Currently there are no statistics tracking available showing direct downloads of the Newsletter from the HIT2GAP webpage.

HIT2GAP Project Team Mailing List – sent to 668 recipients via MailChimp	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subject: HIT2GAP Newsletter Two - November 2016 • Delivered: Nov 07, 2016 3:45 pm 	
Open and Clicks	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open rate 37.06% • List average 36.7% • Industry average (Construction) 19.1% 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Click rate 5.09% • List average 13.1% • Industry average (Construction) 1.8%
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No. of people who opened – 192 • No. of people who clicked – 17 • Bounced – 28 • Unsubscribed – 3 • Successful deliveries – 640 (95.8%) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total opens – 511 (includes multiple by same person) • Forwarded – 0 • Clicks per unique opens – 5.09% • Total clicks – 24

4.3 Flipboard HIT2GAP activity report

Flipboard analytics are a useful instrument to monitor which communications impacted more among the readers, thus helping to elaborate a more concise and targeted communication style. Analytics dashboards provide four metrics regarding the HIT2GAP Magazine statistics:

- Articles by day: Number of published articles (flipped) in the HIT2GAP magazine;
- Viewers by day: Number of readers who have seen items posted in the HIT2GAP magazine;
- Page flips by day: Number of views of per article per day in the HIT2GAP magazine;
- Followers: Number of people who follow the HIT2GAP magazine or are following the magazine authors.

Figure 3 - Cover of HIT2GAP FLIPBOARD Magazine

HIT2GAP Flipboard web version is available here:

<https://flipboard.com/@r2msolution/hit2gap-aeonq1icy>

Till date, the FLIPBOARD activity has grown steadily with the latest figures summarized below:

- Articles: 43
- Viewers: 144
- Followers: 32

Figure 4 - HIT2GAP Flipboard activity (Articles, Followers and Viewers) from Sep 2016 to Feb 2017

4.4 Twitter HIT2GAP account activity Report

Twitter is a leader internet based social network that allows short messages of 140 characters. Its popularity has grown since it was first launched in 2006 and nowadays can be accessed by more than 100 million users worldwide. HIT2GAP twitter account address is <https://twitter.com/HIT2GAP>, while the @HIT2GAP username is used in twitter mobile phone apps. Figure 5 shows a screenshot of the HIT2GAP account feed.

Figure 5: Twitter HIT2GAP account

The HIT2GAP twitter account was created on 6th November 2015. Since then, 46 tweets were written from the account with a significant number of tweets being favoured and retweeted. More than 25,827 impressions have been made by the HIT2GAP tweets, all of which were organic. This means that HIT2GAP tweets have been viewed 25,827 in total. The tweets have generated also 2095 file visits and the @hit2gap account has been mentioned 56 times. The account has 63 followers. The top tweet with 838 impressions was a general tweet announcing the release of the project public reports, made on the 13th Feb 2017. The top mention with 79 engagements, was made by @stephengarvin70, the 22nd Nov 2016, regarding one of the filmclips produced for

HIT2GAP. Figure 6 shows the top tweet and top mention, and Figure 7 shows a summary graph of the HIT2GAP tweeter account data aggregated by month.

Figure 6 - Top Tweet (left) and Top Tweet Mention (right)

Figure 7: Summary Monthly Statistics for HIT2GAP Tweeter Account from Nov 2015 to Feb 2017 to showing Tweeter profile visits, Tweet Impress, Mentions and New Followers.

4.5 Promotional Video Material

Two promotional videos were produced in this period. The first one is a cartoon-style filmclip about the behaviour module. It was produced through APINTECH and was posted on the HIT2GAP website in 2016. The aim of the behaviour modules is to deliver user behaviour information to the building users, to highlight energy wastage and to suggest behavioural and systemic changes. The video is available in the HIT2GAP webpage. <http://www.hit2gap.eu/about-the-project/hit2gap-modules>. Screenshots are shown in Figure 8 and Figure 9, below.

Figure 8 - HIT2GAP Behaviour Module video screenshots

Figure 9 - HIT2GAP Behaviour Module video screenshots

The second video is a filmclip made using student actors, a screenshot of this video is shown in Figure 10. The clip is a narrative story involving different stakeholders involved in a energy review of a building where they are briefed about innovative control technology developed within HIT2GAP. This video was shown internally to all HIT2GAP partners and is currently undergoing further revision.

Figure 10 - HIT2GAP Promotional video produced at BRE

5 COMPENDIUM

A summary of the number of Dissemination and Awareness Activities (D&A) and an estimated reach audience to date is shown in Table 2. This summary corresponds to Reporting Period 1 (M1-M18).

The total figures are approximated.

Table 2 - Compendium of D&A Activities

D&A Activities type	Number	Reach
Scientific – Journal Publications	3	--
Scientific – Conference Participations	3	150
EU research events	2	350
Focus Groups (policymakers, industry, academia)	--	--
Workshops and Industry Conferences	8	1,520
CPD sessions	1	40
Social Media Communications (Flipboard, Web, Tweeter)	90	31,875
Mass Media Communications (TV, Radio, etc.)	1	500
Newsletters	2	593
TOTAL	110	35,028

6 Acronyms and abbreviations

ABO	ABO Data
API	APINTECH
ASC	ASCAMM
BES	Bouygues Energies & Services
BMS	Building Management System
BRE	Building Research Establishment
CPD	Continuous Professional Development
CYL	CYLON
CYR	CyRIC
D&A	Dissemination and Awareness
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
EGE	Ege University
EM	Exploitation manager
ENE	Enerit Ltd.
EU	European Union
EUR	EURECAT
EVL	Evolution
FISE	Fraunhofer ISE
GIR	GIROA
H2020	Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme
LIU	LIUPPA Université de Pau et des Pays de l'Adour
NBK	Nobatek
NSF	National Stakeholders Forum
NUIG	National University of Ireland, Galway
MOS	Mostotal
R2M	R2M Solution
TEK	IK4-TEKNIKER
TL	Task Leader
UDG	University of Girona
UOS	University of Strathclyde
WP	Work Package
WRS	City of Warsaw
ZUT	Zutec

7 ANNEX 1 – Communication Type

WS-IN	Workshop – Industry
WS-PB	Workshop – Professional Body
WS-AC	Workshop - Academic
CPD	Continuous Professional Development
PEV	Partner Events
UPEV	Unique Partner Event
TES	Testimonials
SHF	Stakeholders Forum
CONF	Conference
SEM	Seminar
EU-EEB	Energy Efficient Building Platform events (Build Up – ECTPC, PLEA, etc.)
INEF4	INEF 4 event
EDU	Training and Education Event
H2020	H2020 event
ARTICLE	Article in a Trade Journal, Interest Groups Magazine or Non-Scientific Journals

8 ANNEX 2 – Audience Type

PP	Project Participants
PB	Professional Bodies
G-L	Government – Local
G-N	Government – National
G-EN	Government Energy Agencies
RFA	Research Funding Agency
FI	Financial Institutions
I-BMS	Industry BMS provider, Control Systems
I-SW	Industry - Software Development Companies
I-ESCO	Energy Services Contractors
HEI	Higher Education Institutions. (Universities, Institutes of Technology, Vocational)
RI	Research Institutions
PB-AR	Professional Body - Architecture
PB-EN	Professional Body - Engineering
PB-IT	Professional Body – Information Technology
PB-CM	Professional Body - Construction
PB-BS	Professional Body – Building Services
I-GC	Industry – General Contractors
I-RE	Industry – Real Estate Management Companies
P-FM	Professional – Facility Managers
P-EM	Professionals – Energy Managers
EU-H2020	H2020 project participants
CON	Consumer support body